

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF POLYURETHANE USED AS CORE MATERIAL IN SACRIFICIAL CLADDING FOR BLAST MITIGATION

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ABSTRACT

The increase of the number of intentional and accidental explosions nowadays, explains the interest in the development of suitable blast mitigation systems. One technique uses light weight sacrificial cladding which is composed of a polyurethane core and two thin metallic sheets. The polyurethane (PU) is used to absorb the blast wave energy generated by the explosion and to minimize the residual load applied to the main structure. For numerical prediction of the residual blast loads, one is confronted with the choice to make between different material models that are available in the finite element software, such as for example LS-DYNA. The present paper focuses on the comparison and reliability of the results of blast mitigation predictions with different material models for PU.

Numerical analysis is performed with the following models in LS-DYNA: MAT026 (honeycomb), MAT057 (low density foam), MAT063 (crushable foam), MAT083 (Fu Chang foam), MAT126 (modified honeycomb) and MAT163 (modified crushable foam). These models are first used to simulate a quasi-static uniaxial compression test; the results are compared to experimental ones. Second, blast load conditions are simulated and strain rate effects are studied. The numerical results are compared to the ones obtained with analytical models, such as the one of Hanssen et al. A parametric study looks closer at the foam thickness and compared to the limited foam thickness given by the analytical approach. The paper shows that MAT026, MAT126 and MAT083 give the best agreement with the analytical results. The explanations presented in the paper show that care should be taken when material models have to be selected for numerical analysis of the performance of foam materials in blast mitigation applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing need of protective techniques, that minimize the effects of a blast load, pushes the development of preventive techniques and blast-resistant structures. The main goal is to ensure the survival of people and material in a given facility for a given threat [1]. One technique uses light weight sacrificial cladding which is composed of a polyurethane core and two thin metallic sheets. During the compression mechanism, the polyurethane (PU) is used to absorb the blast wave energy generated by the explosion and to minimize the transmitted load applied to the main structure. The constant plateau stress region over a large range of plastic strain prior to densification is the key to the ability of PU to mitigate a blast load [2].

To select the adequate configuration of the sacrificial cladding (PU and front sheet properties) a suitable numerical model is needed to predict the transmitted loads. One is confronted with the choice to make between different material models that are available in the finite element software, such as for example LS-DYNA. The purpose of the present paper is to compare the reliability of the following material models to simulate the quasi-static and dynamic compression tests: MAT026 (honeycomb),

MAT057 (low density foam), MAT063 (crushable foam), MAT083 (Fu Chang foam), MAT126 (modified honeycomb) and MAT163 (modified crushable foam).

The paper consists of three parts. First, a brief description of the physical properties of PU and the available material models are given. Second, a series of quasi-static compression tests are compared with numerical results. Third, a numerical model of the sacrificial cladding structure is given and compared to the analytical model of Hanssen et al [3].

2 POLYURETHANE BEHAVIOUR AND MATERIAL MODELS

Polyurethane (PU) foams are widely used as energy absorbers. PU materials are used in compression mechanism. The uni-axial compressive stress strain response is divided into three distinct regions: (I) elastic, (II) relatively constant stress and (III) densification (Figure 1) [4]. During elastic loading, the foam material behaviour is governed by the compression and bending of the cell walls comprising the cellular structure and the compression of the trapped gases [4-6]. Continued loading causes the cell walls to buckle and to deform plastically when the foam reaches the “collapsing” stress σ_c , whereby the material undergoes large strain deformation with a minimal increase in stress [7]. Once the cells have fully collapsed, the foam reaches a “locking strain”, whereby small increases in strain result in very large increases in stress [4]. The PU is also simplified by the Rigid-Perfect-Plastic-Locking model (RPPL) where the elastic part is neglected and the behaviour of the compressed foam, at the densification strain ϵ_D , is modelled as a rigid solid.

Figure 1: PU stress-strain response at 0.133 s⁻¹ strain rate

The strain rate is one of the main parameters affecting the stress-strain behaviour of the PU. At high strain rate, the stress-strain profile is similar to the quasi-static behaviour but with an increase of the elastic modulus and the plateau stress. This is due, to the trapped gas (generally air), inside the cellular structure, that is compressed and forced through the foam during loading. The flow rate of the gas is strongly influenced by the compaction rate, and thus the foam material exhibits some strain rate dependency [8].

Several material models are included in the finite element software LS-DYNA able to simulate the PU behaviour such as the MAT026 (honeycomb), MAT057 (low density foam), MAT063 (crushable foam), MAT083 (Fu Chang foam), MAT126 (modified honeycomb) and MAT163 (modified crushable foam).

2.1 Honeycomb and modified honeycomb model (MAT026 & 126)

These material models are developed to simulate the behaviour of metallic foams [9]. The behaviour before compaction is orthotropic where the components of the stress tensor are uncoupled. The mathematical formulation comprises two independent phases: before and after the densification.

Figure 2 Quasi-static compression test and results

The quasi-static compression tests are simulated with LS-DYNA using the material models. The numerical model is given in Figure 3. A 80x80x50mm³ parallelepiped of 2560 solid elements is generated. The one point co-rotational element formulation is used. A rigid body is generated with 1600 shell elements to simulate the top plate of the compression machine. The steel top plate is considered as a rigid material by using the MAT_RIGID keyword. The shell elements are slightly offset from the top surface of the specimen to prevent possible initial penetration issues. An automatic surface to surface contact algorithm is used with a soft constraint-based formulation which is recommended for cases with a large difference of elastic modulus values is available [14]. The load is applied through motion of the top plate shell elements. A prescribed velocity in the z-direction is applied by the Boundary prescribed rigid motion keyword. To replicate the quasi-static loading experienced during testing [15], the velocity field given in equation (1) is applied.

$$v(t) = \frac{\pi}{\pi - 2} \frac{d_{max}}{T} \left[1 - \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2T}t\right) \right] \quad (1)$$

where d_{max} is the maximum displacement of the plate (45mm) and T is the total time of the loading (100ms).

Figure 3 Numerical model of the uni-axial compression test

A typical error that can occur when modelling a foam material subjected to high loads and a large amount of compression is negative volume in the solid elements. This is where one face of a solid element passes through the other face. One method to solve this problem is to increase the stiffness of the foam material as it starts to lock up at about 80-90% crushing (strain = 0.8-0.9). To prevent the numerical instabilities, the time scale factor is reduced to 0.09 from 0.90 (default value). In addition, the hourglass formulation type 4 is used for lower velocities and type 3 for higher velocities.

With the exception of MAT063 where the elastic part is underestimated, the numerical results show a good agreement with the experimental ones (see Figure 4). The main difference between the used material models is the calculation time: the honeycomb and the modified honeycomb material models are more time consuming.

Figure 4 Comparison between the experimental quasi-static uni-axial compression test and the numerical results for several material models

3 DYNAMIC COMPRESSION TEST AND SACRIFICIAL CLADDING EVALUATION

Sacrificial cladding is widely reported in the literature. Analytical, experimental and also numerical studies are carried out to select the optimum configuration and to quantify the absorbed energy. Mainly, metallic cellular materials and structures are used such as Aluminium foam [19], honeycomb, [20] and tubular structure [16,17,18]. PU material is less studied as the core of a sacrificial cladding. This section presents a numerical study of a dynamic compression test using several material models in order to predict the loading transferred to the main structure. The numerical results are compared to the analytical model developed by Hanssen et al. [3]. After that, a parametric study of the foam thickness effect is performed.

3.1 Analytical model

The analytical model can be summarized as an one-dimensional deformation of a foam material under blast loading (Figure 5)

Figure 5 Simplified model of Hanssen et al. [3]

The analytical model is based on the following assumptions:

- the blast load is simplified as a triangular loading,
- the front panel is considered to be rigid,
- the foam material is modelled as a RPPL,
- the foam bar is fixed to a rigid wall at the right side.

The displacement of the front panel, and thus the deformation of the foam bar, is the focus of the analytic model. The analytical model is described by equation 2.

$$\left[M_1 + \frac{\rho_f A}{M_1 \varepsilon_D} u \right] \ddot{u} + \frac{\rho_f A}{M_1 \varepsilon_D} \dot{u}^2 + (\sigma_c - p(t)) \frac{A}{M_1} = 0 \quad (2)$$

With $t = 0 \rightarrow u = 0; \dot{u} = 0;$

where:

- M_1 stands for the front plate mass,
- ρ_f stands for the foam density,
- u stands for the displacement of the front plate,
- A stands for the exposed surface of the front plate to the blast loading.

The blast loading pressure $p(t)$ is defined by equation 3.

$$p(t) = \begin{cases} p_0 \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_0} \right), & t \leq t_0 \\ 0, & t > t_0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where:

- p_0 stands for the initial peak pressure,
- t_0 stands for the duration of the blast loading.

In addition, Hanssen et al. [3] calculated the minimum foam thickness (equation 4) to absorb a given blast load.

$$t_{min} = \frac{I^2}{(M_0 + 2M_1)p_0A\varepsilon_D} \left(\frac{p_0}{\sigma_c} - \frac{4}{3} \right) \quad (4)$$

where:

- M_0 stands for the foam mass,
- $I = \frac{1}{2}p_0t_0A$ stands for the total impulse exerted on the front plate.

The numerical model is given in Figure 6. The model used for the quasi-static compression test is adapted for the present section. The shell front plate is replaced by an elastic 3D plate to simulate the front plate. The blast loading is applied to the upper surface of the front plate using the *Load_Segment_Set keyword. The pressure parameters and the PU properties are kept constant. Only the foam thickness (t_1 , t_2 and t_3) is varied to study the minimum foam length needed (equation 4). The parameters used for the numerical and the analytical models are summarized in Table 2. The analytical model does not consider the strain rate effect. To validate the numerical model, only one stress-strain curve at a specific strain rate is introduced to the material models [4].

Table 2 Parameter combination for numerical simulations

p_0	t_0	σ_c	M_1	t_{min}	t_1	t_2	t_3
[MPa]	[ms]	[MPa]	[kg]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]
6.7	0.388	0.320	0.386	50.8	15	50.8	70

Figure 6 Numerical model of the sacrificial cladding

First, the displacement of the front plate is compared with the analytical model. Second, the minimum foam thickness is evaluated by focusing on the transferred load to the rigid plate. Figure 7 presents the comparison between the analytical front plate displacement and the numerical results using several material models. A good agreement is observed particularly for MAT026 and MAT126.

Figure 7 Comparison between the analytical front plate displacement and the numerical results

Figure 8 shows the foam thickness effect. Only the honeycomb material model is used (MAT026). With a foam thickness lower than minimum length (t_{min}), the complete densification of the PU is reached before the complete absorption of the delivered energy and an abrupt increase of the transmitted load is observed. On the other hand, using t_3 as foam thickness, there is enough foam material to compress before the full densification.

Figure 8 Foam thickness effect of the transmitted stress

4 CONCLUSIONS

The numerical model of a light weight sacrificial cladding, which is composed of a polyurethane core and two thin metallic sheets, is studied. Mainly, the available material models in LS-DYNA are examined to simulate the dynamic behavior of PU: MAT026, MAT126, MAT057, MAT063, MAT163 and MAT083.

The material models are introduced first to predict the quasi-static uni-axial compression test. The results show good agreement comparing with the experimental results. Second, the dynamic compression test is modeled. The strain rate effect is introduced. The numerical result is compared to the analytical model developed by Hanssen et al. [3]. Also, good agreement is recorded.

Hanssen et al. [3] calculated the minimum foam thickness needed to absorb the transferred load. A parametric numerical study of the foam thickness effect is performed. Results show that with a foam thickness lower than minimum length, the complete densification of the PU is reached before the complete absorption of the delivered energy and an abrupt increase of the transmitted load is observed. On the other hand, there is enough foam material to compress before the full densification.

A typical error that can occur when modelling a foam material subjected to high loads and a large amount of compression is negative volume in the solid elements. This problem can be solved by increasing the stiffness of the foam material at the densification region. In addition, numerical instabilities may be resolved by reducing the time scale factor to 0.09 and using the hourglass formulation type 4 for lower velocities and type 3 for higher velocities.

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